

A STUDY ON CONSUMERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ORGANIC PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SALEM CITY

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Abstract:

The organic is the term which is used frequently, now-a day's by the consumers all over the world. The growth of organic food market in India shows that, it's is no longer an exception and the same time when compare to the developed countries like USA, UK and other European countries the awareness and revolution the agricultural industry has made tremendous change in farming the aim of food for every one. Organic food is extremely popular and everyone wants to know about their benefits. The sweeping public opinion that organic food is healthier than conventional food is quite strong, and is the main reason for increase in its demand over the past 5-6 years. Organic Facts is a strong proponent of organic food; however, this website also believes in putting across the most accurate facts to its visitors.

Key Words: Organic Food, Environment, Conventional Food & Consumers

Introduction:

The meaning of organic food is, obtaining agricultural produce without using manmade fertilizers and without harming the environment. Food products obtained by organic farming is called organic food products. As these food products are environmental friendly, the food products are fresh, hygienic and healthy.

Review of Literature:

Samuel K. adungu (2000), finding of his study that awareness level of organic foods is very low in the study area. The unaware people are belonging to the lower income group and in east Africa majority of the population are lower income group hence the percentage of awareness remains at the very level. As the awareness level stayed at lower level the consumption also remained at the lower level and half of the samples have never consumed nor had an idea of consuming it in future.

Maria Raquel Lucas (2008), concluded that they possess average knowledge about the organic food products Lisbon people are more aware than Berlin people. The respondents have positive attitude towards organic like they believed that the organic products are good for health, tastier, better quality than conventional foods. Even the non-buyers of organic food products were approached and the major reason they feel were the price is more for organic products. The authors also analysed the willingness to pay OFP by the respondents and they found that up to 25% increase of price is accepted and the price is accepted and the preference order of OFP is fruits and vegetables then eggs, poultry and meat followed by milk, olive oil etc.,

Need of the Study:

The main purpose of need of the study, the problems faced by people of today's world are work at tension, stress, pollution which leads to various health issues. For past few years people has become more health conscious and started approaching dietitian, nutritionist, gym etc. People perception and nutritional food will give result for health issues. Now people started buying organic food products. So this study is necessary to identify the consumers attitude towards organic food products.

Statement of the Problem:

A study on Organic products analysed by various authors with different perception. The awareness level of consumers towards organic food products are analysed by the authors and found that the awareness is not sufficient for the consumers in the study area Samuel k. Ndungu (2006), Maria Raquel Lucas (2008) Mohamed Altarawnessh (2013). The perception satisfaction level has been analysed by various authors. The review helped to identify the repurchases intention of organic food products consumer as the problem are in the study.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the consumers awareness towards organic food products.
- ✓ To Understand the consumers attitude on organic food products.
- ✓ To study the consumers satisfaction and repurchases intention towards organic food products.

Hypothesis:

- ✓ H_0 – There is no association between gender and satisfaction of consumers
- ✓ H_0 – There is no association between age and awareness level among consumers.
- ✓ H_0 . There is no association between satisfaction and repurchase intention of consumers.

Research Methodology:

The study based on primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected by distributing questionnaire to the organic food product consumes. The Questionnaire has been divided in the four parts namely, demographic, awareness, satisfaction and repurchase of intention. It contains multiple choice and five point likert –scale questions. The secondary data has collected from various books, journals, magazines and newspapers and various reports

Sample Design:

The questionnaire has distributed to 50 respondents at Salem city. The questionnaire was distributed only to consumers only of organic food products. Convenience sampling is adopted in this study.

Result and Discussion:

1. H₀-There is no association between gender and satisfaction of consumers

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp.Sig.(2-sided)
Person Chi-square	13.976	9 ^a	0.123
Likelihood	17.336	9	0.044
Linear-by-Linear Association	.425	1	0.514
N of Valid Cases	50		

From the above table shows that the result of the chi-square test and the Asymp.Sig.,(2.sided) P value is .123 which is greater than .05. The hypothesis is rejected which shows that there is an association between gender and the satisfaction level of consumers.

2. H₀-There is no association between age and the awareness level among consumers

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp.Sig.(2-sided)
Person Chi-square	51.683 ^a	40	0.102
Likelihood	46.870	40	0.211
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.152	1	0.696
N of Valid Cases	50		

From the above table shows that the result of the chi-square test and the Asymp.Sig.,(2.sided) P value is .102 which is greater than .05. The hypothesis is rejected which shows that there is an association between age and the awareness level of consumers.

3. H₀-There is no association between satisfaction and the repurchase level among consumers

Correlations			
	Value	Satisfaction Towards Organic	Repurchase Intention Towards Organic
Satisfaction Towards Organic	Pearson correlation	1	.707
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
Repurchase Intention Towards Organic	Pearson correlation	.707	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	50	50
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)			

The above table shows that the correlation between satisfaction and repurchase intention towards food products are significant. Both are positively correlated and trends to increase in the same direction.

Finding

The study reveals the following results which includes problems as well as positive about the organic food products

- ✓ Nearly 91% of the respondents accepted that the organic food products are healthier safer and contains nutritional values.
- ✓ The problem which the consumers faces was the price and short supply of organic food products.
- ✓ The purchase of organic food products is maximum preferred by females but the knowledge about organic product is possessed more by male.
- ✓ 79% of the respondents are not aware of organic certification in India.
- ✓ The various statistical tools show that customer satisfaction and repurchase intention are positively correlated.

Conclusion:

Organic food product is been accepted as a nutritional food are keeps human healthy in spite of busy work schedule, stress and pollution. The short supply and premium price disturbs the growth of consumption rate. The farmers also show dis-interest towards converting the inorganic into organic farms, because nearly 3 years to convert and the government is not providing any subsidy or any type of motivation. In spite of few

problems the organic food product market is gradually increasing at the same time the government should give more benefits to the farmers.

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